

A Study on Marketing Problems of Women Entrepreneurs: A Literature Review

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Abstract

This paper examines problems faced by women entrepreneurs specifically, the marketing problems of women entrepreneurs for women-owned Micro and Small enterprises (MSEs). It explores and studies various aspects of marketing problems. Along these lines, an analysis of the relevant literature based on a systematic review of articles was conducted on marketing strategy problems and challenges for women entrepreneurs over the last decade in India. These articles have been taken from the leading Entrepreneurship and Strategic Management journals. Women's MSEs face many problems of which business finance, education, family pressure, access to resources, and male dominance are widely discussed. From the business skills viewpoint Marketing Function poses an important challenge to women entrepreneurs. This paper attempts to structure current research reviews of the various literature to understand the description of the problems in marketing strategy design documented in the research studies.

Key Words: MSEs, Women Entrepreneurs, Marketing Problems

Introduction

“Entrepreneurship is not preparation for life, entrepreneurship is life itself.” Women or a group of women who launch and run a commercial enterprise are referred to as women entrepreneurs. An entrepreneurial woman serves several purposes. They ought to investigate the possibilities of starting a new company, take calculated risks, introduce innovation, and handle the business's administration, management, and coordination. The number of female entrepreneurs is rising in practically every nation's economy. The growing awareness of women's roles and economic standing in society, as well as their knowledge, skills, and compliance in corporate endeavours, has increased their latent entrepreneurial potential.

Women are primarily motivated to enter the business world by female entrepreneurs, who offer them the courage to pursue self-sustaining careers and succeed in life. To become financially independent, "women entrepreneurs" must satisfy a personal need, which is the rationale for their autonomous decision-making in both their personal and professional lives. Women who are entrepreneurs have a strong desire to make a huge positive impact. who, in light of the advent of the media, is capable of upholding traditional values in both home and social life. Females are aware of their attributes, entitlements, and professional environments.

Entrepreneurship and Women Entrepreneurs

It may be characterized as a woman or group of women who start, plan, and run a business together. The Government of India defines it further as a business that is owned and managed by a woman, providing at least 51% of the capital and at least 51% of the jobs created by the business to women. This indicates that women cannot be kept at home to get treatment for an extended period. Following the effects of globalization, women are continuously advancing by having a big impact on both home and global realms, in addition to household tasks. It is clear from this instance that women are capable of juggling work and home life. This leads to the conclusion that women.

Ministry of Small, Medium-Sized and Micro Businesses The program is designed specifically to help women craftsmen working in the coir sector advance their skills. This curriculum imparts a two-month instruction in coir spinning. An allowance of Rs. 3,000/-per month is provided to the applicants who complete this training. To establish coir units, the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP) program is urged to provide support to the skilled craftsmen under its purview. In areas where coir fibre is produced, this program supports rural women craftspeople.

Currently, there are more than 400 million female entrepreneurs worldwide. Even though these promising statistics about women entrepreneurs demonstrate tremendous progress, there are still important obstacles that women entrepreneurs must overcome to succeed. Generally speaking, women are still starting their businesses in underdeveloped countries like India. According to the MSME statistics released by the Government of India, the percentage of women entrepreneurs in the MSME sector was 11.5% in 2010 and increased to 18.5% in 2020. Additionally, women-owned enterprises range in age from 12 months to 4 years on average. Women-owned MSEs close down at a relatively high rate. Researching the numerous factors influencing the success of women-owned enterprises is crucial. Numerous research that has been carried out over the past ten years have shown numerous problems.

Objective

This paper presents a structured review of the documentation of the marketing problem faced by women entrepreneurs owning MSE in the research papers and reports. This paper is developed on the literature reviewed selected chronologically. It is primarily to understand the prevalence of the marketing problems through its documentation in the research papers and reports.

Methodology

This paper is exploratory. It conceptually tries to understand the cognizance in the research studies of the marketing problems faced by women entrepreneurs in the MSE sector. The chronologically selected research papers, and reports published by the government, advocacy bodies, research institutions, and academic scholars are selected and studied.

Introduction to MSME and Women Entrepreneurship

According to a report presented by the Inter-Ministerial Committee of the Government of India for Accelerating Manufacturing in Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises Sector, MSMEs account for approximately 7-8 percent of India's GDP, 45 percent of the country's manufacturing output, and 40 percent of its exports. They are acknowledged as the economy's main growth engine. The MSME industry employs the greatest number of people, second only to agriculture. MSMEs are extensively distributed around the nation and provide a broad variety of goods to meet the needs of different market niches. In the context of economic growth with fairness and regional balance, their geographic distribution, varied product offerings, and potential for innovation and employment creation make them crucial (Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises & Lal, 2013). MSMEs are supplementary to major industries as auxiliary units, and this

sector makes significant contributions to the nation's socioeconomic advancement (Government of Tamil Nadu, z.d.).

According to the Ministry of MSME's Udyam Registration Portal (URP), women-owned MSMEs account for 20.5% of all MSMEs registered on the Portal since its launch on July 1, 2020. The employment created by all Udyam registered units is increased by 18.73% by these women-owned MSMEs, accounting for 11.15% of the total investment. The share of women-owned MSMEs in the overall revenue of MSMEs registered with Udyam is 10.22%. According to information gathered from the Udyam Assist Platform (UAP), which is used to register Informal Micro Enterprises (IMEs), women-owned IMEs have contributed 70.49% of all IMEs since the portal's launch on January 11, 2023, and they have contributed 70.84% of employment.

The Ministry of MSME has taken several steps to support women-owned MSMEs

- i. initiatives specifically designed to register women-owned MSMEs using the Udyam Registration Portal.
- ii. To support female entrepreneurs, the Public Procurement Policy was modified in 2018 to require Central Ministries, Departments, and Undertakings to purchase at least 3% of their yearly needs from micro and small businesses controlled by women.
- iii. Two measures for women entrepreneurs have been implemented as of January 12, 2022, to help them under the Credit Guarantee Scheme for Micro & Small Enterprises. These are the following:
 - a. 10% concession in annual Guarantee fees; and
 - b. 10 % additional Guarantee coverage of up to 85%, as against the 75% for other entrepreneurs.
- iv. The Ministry of MSME runs the "Skill Upgradation & Mahila Coir Yojana" under the Coir Vikas Yojana, a special training program designed to improve the skills of women artisans working in the Coir industry, to promote female entrepreneurship.
- v. Additionally, the Ministry oversees the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP), a significant credit-linked subsidy initiative designed to provide prospects for self-employment by establishing microenterprises in the non-farm sector. Higher subsidies are provided to recipients who fall under specific groups, such as Scheduled Caste, Scheduled Tribe, OBC, minorities, women, former service members, physically disabled people, NER, hill and border areas, etc.
- vi. Higher subsidies are offered to women-owned MSMEs under the Procurement & Marketing Support Scheme to promote the involvement of female entrepreneurs in trade shows.

- vii. The "SAMARTH" program was started to help women-owned MSMEs train over 7,500 female applicants from rural and suburban regions and to assist them with skill development and market development. 20% of MSME business delegations for domestic and international exhibitions under the schemes for marketing assistance implemented by the Ministry; 20% off the annual processing fee on the National Small Industries Corporation's Scheme; and 20% seats in free skill development programs organized under the ministry's skill development schemes have been extended to aspiring and current women entrepreneurs.
- viii. The MSME Sustainable Zero Defect Zero Effect (ZED) Certification Scheme is an endeavour aimed at giving Indian MSMEs with an influence on the economy and society a path to global competitiveness in terms of MSMEs' capacity building. The initiative aims to provide items made by MSMEs that are both environmentally friendly and have no recall from the market. Women-owned MSMEs are eligible for a 100% rebate on the cost of ZED Certification under this program designed to encourage and empower female entrepreneurs.
- ix. 18,888 ideas were submitted during the special MSME Idea Hackathon 3.0 for female entrepreneurs, which was held in conjunction with the MSME Innovative Scheme's incubation component.

The size of this sector, both in registered and unregistered forms, is 361.76 lacs, according to the MSME census of India. Personal and home items, clothing, fur pressing and dyeing, food and beverage production, service industries, lodging and dining establishments, sales, research and development, automobiles, and motorcycles are the top industrial sectors in MSME. Textiles, machinery and equipment, fabricated metal items, automobile fuel, and furniture production (Razor Pay Learn, 2021). Any company's fundamental rule of success is its ability to adapt to its surroundings. A nation's ability to grow economically depends on its level of entrepreneurship. Several examples of lone entrepreneurs whose inventiveness sparked the industrialization of several countries may be found throughout history. It is seen as a crucial tool for preventing the consolidation of economic power in a small number of hands, promoting economic dispersion, and achieving a fair distribution of the nation's revenue. It is believed that entrepreneurs play a significant role in economic growth by actively mobilizing resources.

One of the key components of economic progress is entrepreneurship. Due to the creation of new job possibilities, entrepreneurial ventures are significant economic drivers. By joining the industrial ecosystem and functioning as auxiliary units for larger enterprises to support the system's growth, the MSME sector, as

noted in the KPMG 2016 MSME Report (KPMG India, 2016), offers more employment opportunities at a lower capital cost than large enterprises, particularly in rural and remote areas. Particularly for female entrepreneurs, the SME sector has shown to be the most advantageous as it allows them to participate in the economy regardless of their level of education or prior work experience. One notable trend in women-owned enterprises is the prevalence of skill-based business units. They are mainly related to catering and food.

The phenomena of women entering the business world and drawing in economists, legislators, policymakers, and social workers have been extensively covered. Women are less likely than males to participate in the entrepreneurial process, despite persistent attempts. According to the Mastercard Index of Women Entrepreneurs (Mastercard & Prokop, 2022), there are just seven female entrepreneurs in India out of 100. Only 20% of companies in the nation are owned by women, according to Google-Bain research (Google and Bain & Company, 2018). The World Economic Forum's 2021 report also highlighted the stark gender disparity of 72% in India's labor market. Any firm can use marketing strategy as part of its operational or functional plan to reach its objectives in terms of revenue, profit margin, or new markets.

According to Degoma Durie (2016), the firm's marketing capabilities must be used in conjunction with appropriate and well-executed marketing strategies to efficiently direct the deployment of the limited resources in pursuit of the intended goals and objectives. Stated differently, a marketing strategy comprises a comprehensive collection of decisions about the creation and retention of value over an extended duration by the organization. It is a long-term, forward-looking planning strategy whose main objective is to create a competitive edge that will last. Strategic planning is examining the company's strategic starting point before formulating, assessing, and choosing a competitive position that is focused on the market and supports the organization's aims and marketing objectives.

The main goal of marketing strategy is to achieve the firm's goals within a particular product market by efficiently allocating and coordinating marketing resources and operations. It emphasizes how marketing functions as a conduit between a business and its clientele. Essentially, it responds to three very straightforward questions:

- (1) Where are we now?
- (2) Where are we going? And
- (3) how are we going to get there?

Literature Review

Dr. C. K. Patel and P.K. Desai, (Patel et al., 2016), discussed the marketing problems faced by women entrepreneurs in their research study, "*women entrepreneurship development, constraints & problems of women entrepreneurs in India*". They said that structured industries present fierce competition for female entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs have marketing issues because of the intense rivalry in the market and the limited mobility of women. The challenges come in the shape of innovation, lax lending conditions, cheaper alternative product competition, and delayed payment. According to their analysis, female entrepreneurs do not have sufficient market expertise or access. According to their research, there is a widespread practice of selling goods through middlemen. Urban regions may differ, but semi-urban areas have a heavy reliance on the middleman. They also noted how hard it is for female business owners to get into the market and become well-known for their goods. female business owners.

Shivalika Vipul Patel (Patel et al., 2016), in her research study on, "*Women entrepreneurship in India-challenges & prospects*" expressed that lack of Marketing skills and support is one of the most important problems faced by women entrepreneurs. According to her, female entrepreneurs typically have challenges in accessing markets and possess worse marketing abilities in comparison to their male counterparts. Strategic marketing abilities are necessary to both retain current business and pursue new company prospects. According to Patel's study, the company's growth is impacted by their failure to handle marketing activities with a strategic eye.

A report published by Swaniti, (swaniti.com, 2015), stated that Access to Markets and Networks became an important challenge for women entrepreneurs. It is the capacity to enter new markets that call for contacts, knowledge, and skill. Women business owners frequently lack expertise and training, which makes it difficult for them to properly sell their products and services. Because most female entrepreneurs run their businesses on a small scale, they also don't have access to enough market data on costs, inputs, and rivals, let alone leverageable support services.

Deepa Vinay, and Divya Singh (Vinay & Singh, 2015) presented a research study on, the "*Status and Scope of Women Entrepreneurship*". They investigated several barriers to women's entrepreneurship in their research. One of the biggest barriers to expansion, they said, is marketing and market access. They defined it as "market access," which refers to having the capacity to access new markets as well as relationships, knowledge, and competence in those areas. Women are unable to strategically sell products and services

because they do not have access to training and expertise in participating in the marketplace. Furthermore, they frequently don't have exposure to the global market, so they don't know what is considered appropriate elsewhere. One major barrier and disincentive, especially for women-owned enterprises, is the high expense of establishing new business connections and ties in a foreign market or nation. Additionally, women may experience discrimination or fear of sexual.

Meenakshi and Dr. S.N. Mahapatra, (Meenakshi & Mahapatra, 2018), Explained in their research on, “*Constraints faced by women entrepreneurs*” that Marketing and finance are two important problems faced by women entrepreneurs. For women entrepreneurs to participate fully in the company-establishing process, the government ought to offer them financial assistance. They recommended providing distinct facilities so that women may start their businesses fast and simply. Training courses have to be geared toward female company owners and should concentrate on improving their grasp of finance, marketing, and day-to-day operations as well as their entrepreneurial abilities. They observed that intermediaries dominate marketing channels and that police complaint records frequently include instances of financial fraud. These are significant findings. They thus insisted on including mechanisms for marketing and sales support to ensure that intermediaries do not take advantage of female businesses.

V Krishnamoorthy and R Balasubramani (Krishnamoorthy & Balasubramani, 2014) recognized the significance of women's entrepreneurial motivation aspects and its impact on entrepreneurial accomplishments. The study recognized that the key motivators for entrepreneurship include ambition, knowledge and skills, family support, market openness, independence, government subsidies, and commitment fulfilment. The study also concluded that talent and ambition are two distinct aspects of entrepreneurial drive that have a big influence on business performance.

Satpal A, Rupa Rathee and Pallavi Rajain (Satpal et al., 2014) said in their research study on “*Women Entrepreneurship: Challenges in the Present Technological Era*” that women entrepreneurs face problems in managing the marketing activity of businesses as they lack training and strategic understanding of the function. They also brought up the fact that men predominate in the field of marketing. Most female business owners are unable to navigate marketing, distribution, and revenue collecting because they lack an understanding of marketing functions. They need intermediaries for these operations. They said that the intermediaries frequently take advantage of them while seeming to be helpful. They want to increase their profit margin, which hinders the growth of the firm by reducing sales and profit for female entrepreneurs.

Hemant Kumar P. Bulsara, Jyoti Chandwani, and Shailesh Gandhi (P. Bulsara et al., 2014)2, 2014, presented a research case on, “*Women Entrepreneurship in India: A Case Study of Rink’s Creation of Rinku Lakdawala*”. This research case on the fashion design industry was given. They noted in their research investigations that the aforementioned company had serious marketing issues. They observed that there is reluctance and mistrust towards accepting women entrepreneurs in business and industry due to their lack of professional business behaviour. They also saw that the expansion of the firm was hampered by a lack of marketing planning due to new customer anxiety. This shows itself as a slowdown in the economic cycle; recovering finances and promoting products become challenging.

A report published in 2013, by the Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP) (South-West Asia Office (SSWA) & Kumar, 2013) titled “*Creating an Enabling Environment For Women’s Entrepreneurship In India*”, recorded the observation as, women entrepreneurs faced many challenges, specifically in marketing their products. Following the difficulties in obtaining financing, another prevalent issue is advertising their goods or services. Strategic marketing abilities are necessary to grow an existing firm or seize new ones. In situations where they mostly deal with males, female entrepreneurs might not feel as at ease as their male counterparts. They struggle because of psychological and sociocultural issues, which hinder their ability to communicate, negotiate, and win people around to their point of view.

K. Swarnalatha and Anuradha R. K. (Swarnalatha & Anuradha, 2015) presented a research study on, “*Women Entrepreneurship in India Problems and Prospects*”. They made observations on women entrepreneurs' marketing abilities and capabilities in their study. They said that female business owners don't focus on organizing the company's marketing strategy. Their lack of direction and experience in marketing puts them in trouble. According to the findings of their research, women entrepreneurs who want to promote their products must rely on intermediaries who take a big cut of the profits and struggle to establish their brands and get their items noticed.

According to G. Palaniappan, C. S. Ramani Gopal, and A. Mani (Ramani Gopal, et al., 2011), women's internal motivation to launch a business is hampered by the fact that they are not trained in this area. According to their survey, the market and finance are the other two key elements impeding women-owned businesses. They pushed for early training which is still mostly absent today for women who want to pursue entrepreneurship.

Sweta Saurabh (Saurabh, 2011) presented a research study on, *“Issues and challenges faced by women entrepreneurs and their training needs”*. She emphasized in her research the connection between issues encountered and the education needs of female entrepreneurs. 68 per cent of the women entrepreneurs she had chosen for the study spent less than a month to design their firm, while 32 percent required longer than a month, according to her analysis of the entire sample. A whole business strategy was not incorporated in the marketing role, which was cited by 70% of female entrepreneurs as a difficulty. According to the comments, female businesses would rather contract out their marketing. She also emphasized how formal managerial training, entrepreneurial personality qualities, and other aspects affect planning skills. There is evidence that formal training has an impact on planning quality.

Cohoon, Wadhwa, and Mitchell (Cohoon et al., 2010) presented a detailed research study on, *“Understanding of the entrepreneurship - gender-based phenomenon”*. They have presented some significant discoveries, one of which is that women entrepreneurs are a very understudied population. In elucidating the comparative study they showcased, they proposed that initiatives to encourage women in entrepreneurship should guarantee that they have access to networks of mentors and supporters, with a focus on market link, which in their analysis is critical to their success.

Shefali Verma Thakral (Verma Thakral, 2010) In her research study on *“Challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in a developing economy”* highlighted constraints faced by women entrepreneurs. According to her, women's marketing issues were mostly related to location and transportation accessibility. She made clear in her research that to promote women entrepreneurs, policies need to be in place to provide training and guidance.

G. Jayammal (Jayammal, 2009) presented a research study on, *“Problems of women entrepreneurs in Coimbatore”*. According to his analysis, the district's most unresolved issue is the marketing problem. He clarified that depending on local marketplaces and lacking marketing expertise are the main reasons why female entrepreneurs have trouble selling their goods.

Sairabell Kurbah, (KURBAH, 2013) presented a research study on, *“Role of women entrepreneurs in the economic development of Meghalaya: a northeastern state, India”* and pointed out that women entrepreneurs face challenges due to a lack of understanding of competition through are at par in innovativeness with male counterparts. He proposed that women entrepreneurs might enhance their activity, risk-taking, inventiveness, and production by obtaining better education and marketable skills.

Recommendations and Analysis

From the above literature review it is evident that with many other factors listed as challenges to women entrepreneurs, Another significant issue is coming from the marketing department. The following points, which are a component of the marketing strategy designing process, have been documented by the literature review. The literature research makes it clear that developing a marketing strategy is a difficult task for female businesses. Their ignorance of the marketing role and their lack of fundamental marketing abilities are the issues that have been found. Researchers have also noted that inadequate education and training may be the cause of a lack of knowledge of the marketing role. According to researchers, there are a variety of reasons why women entrepreneurs may not have equal access to networking opportunities, training, and mentorship, which has an impact on how they handle marketing initiatives. Scholars have observed that female entrepreneurs exhibit deficiencies in company planning; this might also be connected to these entrepreneurs' marketing performance. The difficulties encountered by female entrepreneurs as reported in the literature study are covered in the table below, along with the grouping they belong to when it comes to the marketing strategy element.

Table 1: The Component of marketing strategy and challenges faced by women entrepreneurs recorded in the literature reviewed

Marketing strategy components	Marketing strategy Sub-activity	Observations documented in Literature Reviewed
What to sell	Product and service planning	They know their product and service very well.
How much to sell	Production and distribution planning, resource planning	Lack of planning, and knowledge (Meenakshi & Mahapatra, 2018) (Satpal et al., 2014) (Swarnalatha & Anuradha, 2015)
At what price to sell	Profit goals, growth goals, pricing	lack of skill and training (swaniti.com, 2015) (Krishnamoorthy & Balasubramani, 2014) (Satpal et al., 2014)
How to sell	Mode of selling – online, offline, B2B, B2C, Advertising, market awareness, customer connect	lack of planning, business skills, and training, (swaniti.com, 2015), (Meenakshi & Mahapatra, 2018) (Satpal et al., 2014) (P. Bulsara et al., 2014) (Swarnalatha & Anuradha, 2015) (Ramani Gopal, et al., 2011)
Where to sell	Distribution planning	Face male dominance, outsourcing, lack of skill, and limited mobility (Patel et al., 2016)

		(Krishnamoorthy & Balasubramani, 2014) (Swarnalatha & Anuradha, 2015) (Saurabh, 2011)
How to compete	How business will handle the market competition? Strengths and challenges	lack of understanding (Krishnamoorthy & Balasubramani, 2014) (P. Bulsara et al., 2014)
Where to compete	Which are the business areas/ grounds where business can face competition other than geography as one parameter	lack of planning training, and networking, (swaniti.com, 2015) (Satpal et al., 2014) (P. Bulsara et al., 2014)

Conclusion

The challenges experienced by female entrepreneurs operating in the MSE sector have been highlighted by several research on women entrepreneurs. One of the issues that has not received enough attention is marketing function planning. One of the main obstacles to the marketing planning role is seen to be a lack of mentorship opportunities and training. In addition to the dominance of males in distribution logistics, women entrepreneurs also confront several socioeconomic barriers that restrict their mobility. The literature review's temporal analysis clearly shows how persistent these issues are. There is a great deal of need for a study to get a more in-depth understanding of the causes of the marketing function difficulties faced by female entrepreneurs.

From the discussion above, it is clear that women-owned businesses in India face several challenges. Challenges in the areas of social, economic, personal, marketing, technology, education, competitiveness, management, and so forth face women entrepreneurs. For firms to become efficient in the current global market, the nation's economic policy climate needs to be favourable. Given that India is a developing nation, the government must encourage entrepreneurship more. Today's government offers a plethora of beneficial programs for both women and young people looking for work. Today, all we need to do is instil in the young a sense of entrepreneurship.

Women's job chances may be impacted by sociocultural factors. For the proportion of women to survive, problems inside their homes must be resolved. In addition to increasing awareness of gender issues, technology that lightens the load on women has to be implemented. Among the difficulties MSMEs in India confront are the total lack of comprehensive and effective financing, rising credit costs, the lack of a counterparty requirement, and restricted access to working capital. Problems with supplies to departments and

ministries as well as organizing production at a sustainable pace are further obstacles. Other significant issues include specifications, product designs, bandwidth, and the total lack of viable competition.

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